

Synthesis, structure, spectra and redox behavior of a ruthenium(III) complex with a tripodal Schiff base ligand

Soma Deoghoria, Sushama Sain, Tapan K. Karmakar, Sujit K. Bera and Swapan K. Chandra*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, India

E-mail : dr_swapan@sify.com Fax : 91-342-530452

Manuscript received 27 July 2001; revised 11 June 2002, accepted 12 July 2002

The reaction of equimolar proportion of septadentate tripodal Schiff base ligand, tris[2-salicylidene(amino)ethyl]amine, H_3L (1) and $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ in refluxing methanol in presence of alkali has afforded a dark coloured compound of composition $[Ru^{III}L].CH_2Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$. X-Ray analysis of the complex shows that the septadentate ligand is coordinated octahedrally to ruthenium and tripodal nitrogen is not in bonding distance ($Ru \dots N(1) = 3.545(12) \text{ \AA}$) to ruthenium. The complex is redox-active and displays one one-electron reduction and one one-electron oxidation couples with $E_{1/2}$ values -0.58 and 0.61 V vs SCE, respectively.

There is continued current interest in ruthenium(III) Schiff base chemistry owing to its importance in organic transformation reactions and oxidation processes¹. These mostly contain carbonyl, halide and triphenylphosphine or triphenylarsine as co-ligands². The coordination chemistry of the septadentate Schiff base ligand H_3L (1) has received some attention³. However, ruthenium chemistry with such ligand system supported by single crystal X-ray structure remains almost unexplored⁴. Herein, we report the synthesis, spectral characterization, X-ray structure and redox behavior of a ruthenium(III) complex incorporating septadentate Schiff base ligand, H_3L (1).

Results and Discussion

$[Ru^{III}L]$ has been prepared by reacting H_3L with $RuCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ in refluxing methanol in the presence of KOH,

Microanalytical results are in line with proposed formulation. In acetonitrile and nitromethane, the compound behaves as non-electrolyte⁵, as indicated by their very low Λ_M values ($5-7 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$). The magnetic moment in polycrystalline form is 1.83 B.M. at 25° , corresponding to a low-spin (idealised t_{2g}^5 , $S = 1/2$) electronic configuration with one unpaired electron as expected⁶. The complex exhibits several absorption bands and shoulders in the 800–300 nm region. The low energy transitions are assignable to be LMCT [phenolate-to-ruthenium(III)] type⁷. The EPR

spectrum recorded in dichloromethane-toluene (1 : 1) solution at -196° shows a distorted octahedral environment with three g-values ($g_1 = 2.18$, $g_2 = 2.16$ and $g_3 = 2.08$).

Crystals of composition $[Ru^{III}L].CH_2Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$ were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into dichloromethane solution of the complex. The perspective view of $[Ru^{III}L]$ is given in Fig. 1. Selected bond parameters are listed in Table 1. The coordination around ruthenium is distorted octahe-

Fig. 1. Perspective view and atom labelling scheme of $[Ru^{III}L]$.

dral as expected. The bond angle about ruthenium in the complex shows significant distortions (Table 1) from octahedral arrangement. The bond distances around ruthenium atom are : Ru-O(1), 2.016(11); Ru-O(2), 2.026(10); Ru-O(3), 2.036(11); Ru-N(2), 2.043(12); Ru-N(3), 2.043(14)

Table 1. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for [Ru^{III}L].CH₂Cl₂.H₂O

Bond length :			
Ru-O(1)	2.016(11)	Ru-O(2)	2.026(10)
Ru-O(3)	2.036(11)	Ru...N(1)	3.545(12)
Ru-N(2)	2.043(12)	Ru-N(3)	2.043(14)
Ru-N(4)	2.102(15)	Cl(1)-C(28)	1.675(25)
Cl(2)-C(28)	1.727(27)		
Bond angle :			
O(1)-Ru-O(2)	87.4(5)	O(1)-Ru-O(3)	85.5(5)
O(2)-Ru-O(3)	86.8(5)	O(1)-Ru-N(2)	91.7(5)
O(2)-Ru-N(2)	175.1(5)	O(3)-Ru-N(2)	88.2(5)
O(1)-Ru-N(3)	87.0(5)	O(2)-Ru-N(3)	91.4(5)
O(3)-Ru-N(3)	172.4(5)	N(2)-Ru-N(3)	93.5(5)
O(1)-Ru-N(4)	171.4(5)	O(2)-Ru-N(4)	85.4(5)
O(3)-Ru-N(4)	89.5(5)	N(2)-Ru-N(4)	95.1(6)
N(3)-Ru-N(4)	97.7(5)		

and Ru-N(4), 2.102(15) Å. These observed distances are within ranges for that of authentic Ru^{III}-O and Ru^{III}-N distances reported in literature⁸. The tripodal nitrogen atom is not coordinated (Ru.....N(1) = 3.545(12) Å) to ruthenium atom.

In acetonitrile solution, the complex displays two metal-centre redox couples under very careful cyclic voltammetry experiments. The first reduction (eq. 2) $E_{1/2}$ at -0.58 V and a second oxidation (eq. 3) $E_{1/2}$ at 0.61 V are with respect to saturated calomel electrode as reference. The peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) for these couples lies in the 60–80 mV range and remains unaltered upon changing scan rates, indicating the reversible nature of the reduction and oxidation.

Experimental

Commercially available RuCl₃.xH₂O was treated with conc. HCl and evaporated couple of times to get RuCl₃.3H₂O⁹. The ligand H₃L was prepared as reported earlier¹⁰. The purification of MeCN, CH₂Cl₂ and the preparation of supporting electrolyte ([Et₄N][ClO₄]) for spectroscopic and/or electrochemical work were executed following reported method¹¹. All other solvents and chemicals were of analytical grade and used as received.

Electrical conductivity (in MeCN/MeNO₂, solute ca. 10⁻³ M), electronic spectrum (in MeCN, solute ca. 10⁻³ M)

spectrum were recorded using a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge and a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer, respectively. C, H and N were analyzed on a Perkin-Elmer 240C instrument. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. X-Band EPR spectra were collected on a Varian E-109C spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar flask for low-temperature measurements (liquid nitrogen, -196°); DPPH ($g = 2.0037$) was used to calibrate the EPR spectra. Electrochemical measurements were performed (in MeCN at 25°) under dry N₂ with a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system as described elsewhere¹². In cyclic voltammetry (CV), following parameters and relation were used : scan rate (ν), 50 mV s⁻¹; formal potential, $E_{1/2} = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively; ΔE_p is the peak-to-peak separation. The potentials are referenced to a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and are uncorrected for junction contributions.

Synthesis of complex : To a methanolic solution (25 cm³) of H₃L (0.5 g, 1.1 mmol) was added RuCl₃.3H₂O (0.29 g, 1.1 mmol), followed by methanolic KOH (0.185 g, 3.3 mmol) solution. The mixture was then refluxed for 3 h resulting brown solution, which was evaporated to dryness. The residue was redissolved in dichloromethane (25 cm³) and layered with hexane (50 cm³). After 2–3 days dark coloured crystals were obtained, and used for X-ray crystallographic work. The product was dried *in vacuo*, (0.49 g, 80%) (Found : C, 58.2; H, 4.8; N, 10.1. C₂₇H₂₇N₄O₃Ru calcd. for : C, 58.3; H, 4.9; N, 10.1%), M_r 5 (MeCN), 7 (MeNO₂) Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹; λ_{max} (10⁻³ ε, mol⁻¹ dm³ cm⁻¹), 730 (0.70, sh), 620 (1.1), 410 (5.0), 340 nm (5.2); $E_{1/2}$ -0.58, 0.61 V.

X-Ray data collection and structure determination : A crystal (0.18 × 0.24 × 0.32 nm³) was mounted on a glass fibre. Data were collected at 20° on a Siemens R3m/V diffractometer with graphite-monochromated MoK_α ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) radiation in ω -2 θ scan mode. Crystal data, data collection and refinement parameters are listed in Table 2. Unit cell parameters were determined by the least-squares fit of the 25 machine-centered reflections ($2\theta = 15$ –30). Systematic absences led to the identification of space group $P2_1/c$. Two-check reflections were measured after every 98 reflections during data collection to monitor crystal stability and showed no significant intensity reduction. Lorentz and polarization corrections were done. Empirical absorption correction could not be made due to unavailability of reflections of sufficient intensity in the required angular ranges. This however is not a vitiating factor since the absorption coefficient (0.770 mm⁻¹) is small. Data reduction

Table 2. Crystal data and structure refinement for the complex $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{31}\text{Cl}_2\text{RuN}_4\text{O}_4$
Formula weight	659.5
Temperature (K)	296
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
Unit cell dimensions	
a (Å)	12.602(6)
b (Å)	14.349(7)
c (Å)	15.948(10)
β (°)	92.06(5)
Volume (Å ³)	2882.0(10)
Z	4
Density (calcd.) (mg m ⁻³)	1.520
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	0.770
$F(000)$	1348
θ range for data collection (°)	2.0 to 25.0
Index ranges (h, k, l)	-13/12, 0/17, 0/18
Reflections collected	9160
Independent reflections	4569 [$R(\text{int}) = 0.021$]
Reflections observed [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	1334
No. of parameters refined	220
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.66
R^a	0.0573
wR	0.0576
Largest diff. peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.55 and -0.47

and all calculations related to structure solution were carried out using SHELXTL-PLUS program system and crystal structure plot was drawn using ORTEP-3¹³. The structure was solved by direct methods. Due to paucity of data only Ru atom, all O and N atoms and solvent molecules were refined anisotropically.

Supplementary material available : Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for the structure reported in this paper have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre as supplementary publication CCDC 153160. Copies of atomic coordinates, bond lengths and angles, anisotropic displacement parameters, hydrogen atom coordinates, torsion angles can be obtained, free of charge¹⁴.

Acknowledgement

Crystallography was done at the National Single Cryst-

tal Diffractometer Facility, Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata. Financial support from U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, India, is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are thankful to Prof. A. Chakravorty, Kolkata, India, for help.

References

1. A. M. El-Hendawy and M. S. El-Shahawi, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 2813; C. M. Che, C. Ho and T. C. Lan, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1991, 129; M. Menon, S. Choudhury, A. Pramanik, A. K. Deb, S. K. Chandra, N. Bag, S. Goswami and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 57; M. M. T. Khan, N. H. Khan, R. T. Kureshy, A. B. Boricha and A. Z. Shaikh, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **170**, 213; M. M. T. Khan, A. S. Misra, P. Rao and Ch. Sreelatha, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1988, **44**, 107; P. Viswanathamurthy, N. Dharmaraj, S. Anuradha and K. Natarajan, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 337; D. Bhattacharya, S. Chakravorty, P. Munshi and G. K. Lahiri, *Polyhedron*, 1999, **18**, 2951; H. L. Kwong and W. S. Lee, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 1999, **2**, 66.
2. R. Ramesh, P. K. Suganthi and K. Natarajan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1996, **26**, 47; M. M. T. Khan, D. Srinivas, R. I. Kureshy and N. H. Khan, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 2320.
3. S. K. Chandra, P. Chakravorty and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 863.
4. Z. Shirin and R. N. Mukherjee, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**, 2625.
5. W. J. Greary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
6. G. K. Lahiri, S. Bhattacharya, B. K. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 4324.
7. K. S. Murray, A. M. van der Bergen and B. O. West, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **105**, 203.
8. C. E. B. Evans, G. P. A. Yap and R. J. Crutchley, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 6161; E. L. Lebeau, S. A. Adeyemi and T. J. Meyer, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 6476; V. Manivannan, B. K. Dirghangi, C. K. Pal and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **36**, 1526.
9. E. A. Seddon and K. R. Seddon, "The Chemistry of Ruthenium," Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
10. D. F. Cook, D. Cummins and E. D. McKenzie, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 1369.
11. D. T. Sawyer and J. L. Roberts, "Experimental Electrochemistry for Chemists", Wiley, New York, 1974, p. 167.
12. S. K. Chandra and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 760.
13. G. M. Sheldrick, SHELXTL-PLUS 88, Structure Determination Software Programs, Nicolet Instrument Corporation, Madison, WI, 1988; L. J. Farrugia, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1997, **30**, 565.
14. Address to Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, U.K. (Fax : 44-1223-336033 or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).